

VENTILATOR ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA: EFFECTIVENESS OF NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO PREVENT VAP

Ghazal Naeem¹, Waseem Sajjad^{*2}, Samreen Nadia³, Ayesha Hussain⁴, Nabila Shafi⁵,
Hina Naeem⁶, Dr. Sahib Zada Ibrar Naeem⁷

^{1,3,4,5,6,7}Dir College of Nursing & Allied Health Sciences, Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

^{*2}Assistant Professor RMI, Peshawar, Pakistan

^{*2}waseemtimergara@gmail.com

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-3311-2250>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20324674>

Keywords

Ventilator Associated Pneumonia; intensive care unit; adults; critically ill patients; preventive measure.

Article History

Received: 14 December 2025

Accepted: 29 January 2026

Published: 13 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Waseem Sajjad

Abstract

Introduction: Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP) is still a concern for individuals who are dependent on a ventilator. It is envisaged that the growth of technology-based innovations would lead to the creation of remedies for the prevention of VAP.

Objective: Effectiveness of non-pharmacological approaches to prevent VAP among patients on MV.

Materials & methods: Prospective, analytical study design selected for the study. Participants recruited via probability sampling technique. VAP preventive measure checklist used to collect data of study respondents.

Results: Total 247 critically ill patients selected for the study out of which majority of participants were male. Preventive care approaches performed in all patient's inclusive head of the bed was always elevated at an angle of 30–45 degrees of 95.14% patients whereas 4.86% were avoided. Whereas cuff pressure of 3.24% study respondents was never maintained; 1.62% seldom maintained; 89.88% participants mostly maintained and remaining 5.26% always. While 4.45% patients tracheostomy tube was replaced without following aseptic technique; 0.40% respondent seldom; 84.21% participants were mostly and remaining 10.93% always.

Conclusion: Consequently, non-pharmacological approaches found to be effective in reducing VAP in critically ill patients and total prevalence of VAP was 4.86% found in critically ill patients.

INTRODUCTION

Background:

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a hospital-acquired infection that occurs most frequently in the ICU, being a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in critically ill patients in the ICU undergoing invasive mechanical ventilation via endotracheal tube (ETT) or

tracheostomy.¹ VAP was estimated to occur at a rate of 3% per day on the first five days, 2% per day on days 6 to 10, and 1% per day after day 10. The diagnostic clinical trial for VAP consists of signs of infection, including fever, purulent discharge, and leukocytosis, along with bacteriological evidence of lung infection and radiological findings suggestive of lung infection.²

It can be defined as a type of lung infection that occurs in people who are on mechanical ventilation breathing machines in hospitals. As such, VAP typically affects critically ill persons that are in an intensive care unit (ICU) and have been on a mechanical ventilator for at least 48 hours.³

In addition, prevalence of VAP was 15.6% (293/1873), of which there were differences between geographical areas. Incidence ranges from 2.86 to 125 cases per 1000days of mechanical ventilation depending on the resuscitation unit.⁴ Intubation was the primary risk factor, associated with more than 95% of pneumonia in the ICU; however, patients with reduced consciousness, trauma, older age and illness severity also have an increased risk.⁵ Other studies showed that the incidence of VAP was higher in older adults aged 65-74 years. Age was related to the body's physiological function, immunological response, and comorbid conditions, which often cause mortality in VAP patients in the ICU. Age influences mortality risk following previous research that the physiological function of body organs decreases in old age. In geriatric patients with comorbidities, especially heart disease, the patient's risk of mortality will increase.⁶

Despite potential factors for these heightened risks, they may include less strict adherence to standard prevention strategies impaired disease- and therapy-associated immune function, prolonged sedation, more frequent need for prone ventilation, and an increased risk for pulmonary infarction and related super-infection.⁷ Preventive bundle approaches reduced the incidence of VAP. However, VAP prevention bundles were composed of different items and may vary substantially between institutions. Each item considered for the prevention of VAP (i.e., included in the VAP prevention bundle).⁸ On the other side, significant gap while implementing preventive care bundle included limited staff resources and time constraints as well as specific local challenges. Effective strategies may include team training, electronic reminders, checklists, and regular feedback to the team.⁹

Likewise, elevating upper body of invasive

ventilated patients was an effective strategy to reduce the risk of micro aspirations and VAP, particularly when the semi-recumbent position (45° elevation) was used. Prone position might reduce VAP rates compared to the supine position although likely to a lesser extent and with inconclusive evidence. However, the prone position has demonstrated a more significant reduction in mortality in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome. Of course, prone positioning remains a hallmark in the therapy of moderate to severe acute respiratory distress syndrome.¹⁰

As well as Endotracheal tubes (ETT) with subglottic secretion drainage designed to remove secretions above the cuff that can cause VAP via micro aspiration have shown a significant reduction in VAP rates.¹¹ Furthermore, closed endotracheal suctioning systems while demonstrating a statistically significant association with VAP reduction have conflicting evidence regarding their overall efficacy particularly as they did not show a reduction in mortality and were associated with a high risk of bias in the studies, especially due to the impossibility of blinding.¹²

Besides, the combination of chlorhexidine with tooth-brushing was more satisfactory in preventing VAP in patients on mechanical ventilation, compared with chlorhexidine alone.¹³ Hence, intubation cuff pressure was one of the critical components of the prophylactic care bundle because ensuring pressure by the cuff reduces the risk of upper respiratory tract secretions flowing to the lower respiratory tract and lungs. It should be continuously maintained between 20 and 30 cm H₂O and measured at least four times daily.¹⁴

Most causes of VAP occurred due to environmental factors, nosocomial infections, and nurses. According to previous study, the occurrence of VAP was not only caused by environmental and hygienic factors, but also as a result of nurses' failure to regulate and maintain the cleanliness of patients who have ETT implanted.¹⁵ Now-a-days technology-based improvements that can undoubtedly ease the job of nurses in a variety of areas, from monitoring

and assessment to the prevention of VAP were now being developed. However, the most important thing to remember was that the innovations made must be precise and able to be assessed precisely. A user-friendly, easy to install, and maintain program would also be a very useful factor in this case.¹⁶ Micro aspiration and translocation from the mouth into the respiratory system have both been implicated in the development of VAP.¹⁷

Furthermore, technology-based innovations can provide new insights for nurses, increase knowledge, and skills in providing nursing interventions. The results of previous studies indicated that with technology-based innovations as well as being innovative and application, it can increase the knowledge and skills of nurses.¹⁸ In future VAP studies, further non-pharmacological interventions should be considered, such as early mobilization, targeted nutrition therapy, appropriate nurse-patient ratios, and inter-professional communication. These have been widely studied and show promising benefits, though their direct impact on reducing VAP outcomes remains uncertain. Until more robust evidence is available, the multidisciplinary team should carefully select prevention measures. Given these challenges, further high-quality, (cluster) randomized controlled trials are crucial to establish the effectiveness of VAP prevention interventions. Therefore, this study aims to assess the effectiveness of preventive care bundle approaches to reduce VAP at a public sector hospital, Lahore.

1.1. Problem statement/significance of the study

The incidence of VAP in developing countries is much higher than that in developed countries. The reason is that developing countries do not have a good preventive strategy for VAP. It is very important to identify the risk factors of VAP for guiding the clinical prevention of VAP. VAP preventive measures for risk factors consisted of spontaneous breathing trial and daily awakening trial to reduce mechanical ventilation time and hospitalization time; Head of bed elevation to

30–45 degrees, reducing unnecessary sputum suction and reducing the replacement of ventilator circuit to reduce aspiration; Selective decontamination of the digestive tract and selective oropharyngeal decontamination to reduce the colonization of drug-resistant bacteria. In fact, the above preventive measures are often used together clinically, called VAP prevention bundle. VAP prevention bundle requires not only multi-preventive measures to be used together but also requires medical staff and patients to carry out safety education in order to better improve the operational ability of medical staff and patients' compliance. However, appropriate quantification of the impact and burden of un-prevented VAP is imperative to understanding its severity and the importance of additional preventive measures and timely treatment. Although its occurrence is reported to be associated with increased ICU mortality. Estimation of the causal impact of HAIs, however, remains subtle and controversial because such assessments are based on either observational data or randomized trials with varying levels of preventive effectiveness. Hence, this study will have significant impact on future mortality rate of VAP as innovative VAP bundle care helps to improve patients outcome if used properly and consistently and proper training of nursing and paramedical staff.

1.2. Research objectives

To determine preventive care strategies used in ICU to prevent ventilator associated pneumonia at a public sector hospital, Lahore.

To assess which is most effective preventive care used to improve patient's outcome with VAP at public sector hospital, Lahore.

To assess prevalence of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients admitted in adult ICU at a public sector hospital, Lahore.

1.3. Research questions

What type of preventive care strategies used in ICU to prevent ventilator associated pneumonia at a public sector hospital, Lahore?

What was the most effective preventive care used to improve patient's outcome with VAP at

public sector hospital, Lahore?
How much prevalence of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients admitted in adult ICU at a public sector hospital, Lahore?

1.4. Key term definition (Operational)

Ventilator associated with Pneumonia (VAP)

Patients ventilated for >48 hours diagnosed with VAP based on the presence of new and/or progressive pulmonary infiltrates on the chest radiograph plus two or more of the following criteria: fever >38.5°C or hypothermia <36°C, leukocytosis $\geq 12 \times 10^9/L$, purulent tracheobronchial secretions, and a $\geq 15\%$ reduction in PaO_2/FiO_2 .

Preventive care bundle

“A small, straightforward set of evidence-based practices (generally three or more) that, when performed collectively and reliably, have been proven to improve patient outcomes set of care practices.”

MATERIALS & METHODS

3.1. Study design

This was prospective cohort study, in other words analytical observational study design adopted in this research work.

3.2. Study setting

This study was conducted at Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore.

3.3. Study duration

Research was conducted for the period of one year from 1st Jan 2024 to 31st Dec 2024.

3.4. Sample size

To calculate sample size for cohort studies, we need the following: Conventionally, alpha (two-sided) = 0.05 (or 5%) and beta = 0.20 (or 20%).

The formula to calculate sample size for cohort study. Thus, required sample size for the study is 247 patients with VAP Sampling technique Probability, simple random sampling technique.

3.5. Sample selection criteria

a. Inclusion criteria

Participants were recruited on behalf of listed below criteria:

- Both male and female admitted in adult ICU.
- Who received mechanical ventilator (>48-h).
- Or progressive radiographic infiltrate who have Temperature of >38°C or <36°C.
WBC > 12000/ microliter or < 4000/ microliter.
Persistent bronchial secretions & Impaired PaO_2/FiO_2 ratio.

b. Exclusion criteria

Participants were excluded on behalf of the criteria listed below:

- “Normal respiratory flora,” “normal oral flora,” “mixed respiratory flora,” “mixed oral flora,” “altered oral flora.”
- Isolation of commensal flora of the oral cavity or upper respiratory tract.
- Any coagulase-negative Staphylococcus species.
- Those having pulmonary infection at the time of admission or shifted from other hospital with Endotracheal Tube (ET).
- Those known to be HIV positive.
- With evidence of pneumonia before being intubated/ventilated: fever, cough, chest pain, rales on auscultation, chest X- ray with damage.

Data collection procedure

Researchers record every day the number of new patients admitted to the department who have been previously intubated, or patients currently being treated in the department who have been intubated. Then, researchers collected clinical information of study participants with blood tests, blood gases, and chest X-rays after 2 days of mechanical ventilation or when there were clinical signs suspicious of pneumonia. Following preventive measures carried out for among study participants to assess the effectiveness of VAP

include Hand hygiene; Patients were monitored through in-person observation during the day and camera observation at night. The Vital Signs and Treatment form filled out three times a day. Then, elevated head 30- 45 degrees: Place the patient in a position with the head of the bed raised above 30° (in case there are no contraindications). Angle of the patient's joint measured three times a day at the bedside using a protractor and recorded in the nurse's monitoring chart. Afterwards, oral hygiene: After pharyngeal suction, oral hygiene performed with a solution containing 0.12% chlorhexidine. Patient's vital signs were also recorded daily from the nurse's bedside monitoring board. Additionally, using a checklist, patients observed via camera at least once daily. After this, manage the breathing circuit: 25-30 cm H₂O manometer thrice daily at random intervals. Next, preventive care approach was cuff pressure control: It breathing circuit was not changed periodically; only changed it when visibly dirty or damaged. Researchers recorded patient observations three times per day on the bedside monitoring board. Next step was subglottic secretion suction: Patient has an endotracheal tube suctioned on the cuff, intermittent suction every 4 h, or continuous suction. If the patient had a suction endotracheal tube on the cuff but was not suctioned, if it was noncompliant. Then, researchers monitored suctioning chart once a day maintained by nursing staff based on their work shift. Afterwards, patients performed the spontaneous breathing test and assessed for daily estimation. As well as, during the day shift, patients allowed to sit at a height of 70-90 degrees or get out of bed early at least once and they were instructed to perform exercise daily and waking time was also recorded in the nursing

chart. Patients were evaluated daily using the care bundle application evaluation form. For all these preventive measures, their compliance / non-compliance and their final consequence related to the occurrence of VAP were determined. Finally, gathered data was shared with HOD to validate the information.

Ethical consideration

After obtaining approval of Institutional Review Board of Khyber Medical University, Peshawar. Research work was initiated and purpose of the study cleared to HOD of adult ICUs of Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore. Upon admittance, accompanying relatives or if patient was awake and conscious, they were informed about study purpose. Verbal and written informed consent obtained from patient's attendant. By omitting patient names from the proforma, confidentiality was upheld throughout study period.

Data analysis:

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, 2024) was used to analyze research data. Simple descriptive analysis was used to represent data in the form of frequencies and percentages. Furthermore, Microsoft Spreadsheet was used to display data in tables.

RESULTS

Total 247 patients selected from adult ICUs have aged from 18 years to >69 years. Majority of study respondents were male and having age >69 years. 27.13% of respondents from M.I.C.U.; 27.94% were taken from S.I.C.U.; 31.58% study participants from C.I.C.U. while 9.31% from E.C.U. and only 4.05% from others I.C.U. as table 4.1. summarizes socio-demographic characteristics of study respondents.

Table 4.1.: Socio-demographic characteristics of patients (n=247)

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
18-28 years	12	4.86
29-38 years	9	3.64
39-48 years	22	8.91
49-58 years	31	12.55
59-68 years	72	29.15
>69 years	101	40.89
Total	247	100.00
Gender		
Male	216	87.45
Female	31	12.55
Total	247	100.00
Level of education		
SSC/HSC	212	85.83
Graduate	12	4.86
Masters	9	3.64
Others	14	5.67
Total	247	100.00
Admitted in ICU		
MICU	67	27.13
SICU	69	27.94
CICU	78	31.58
ECU	23	9.31
Others	10	4.05
Total	247	100.00
Religion		
Muslim	234	94.74
Non-Muslim	13	5.26

Total	247	100.00
Household income		
Low	126	51.01
Medium	112	45.34
High	9	3.64
Total	247	100.00

As it was prospective observational study, so a (checklist-VAP prevention) was used to assess frequency and effectiveness of preventive care performed among patients on mechanical ventilation. Head of the bed was always elevated at an angle of 30–45 degrees of 95.14% patients whereas 4.86% were avoided. Whereas cuff pressure of 3.24% study respondents was never maintained; 1.62% seldom maintained; 89.88% participants mostly maintained and remaining 5.26% always maintained as indicated in table 4.2.

In the sample of 247 patients, 2.02% were never performed oral care with chlorhexidine; 2.83% respondents were seldom performed; 19.03% participants were mostly performed, and rest of 76.11% study respondents were always

performed. Meanwhile, following aseptic techniques also reduced VAP among patients on MV, so, 4.45% patients tracheostomy tube were replaced without following aseptic technique; 0.40% respondent seldom; 84.21% participants were mostly and remaining 10.93% always as shown in table 4.2. Overall, elevating head of the bed at an angle of 30–45 degrees, maintaining cuff pressure at 20–30 cm H₂O, oral care with chlorhexidine and following aseptic techniques before replacement of tracheostomy tube having direct impact to prevent VAP among patients on MV. Hence, 12 patients diagnosed with VAP during the study did not perform preventive care plan regularly. Total prevalence of VAP was 4.86% among patients on MV.

Table 4.2.: Preventive measures performed at ICUs to prevent VAP among patients on mechanical ventilation (n=247)

Sr. no.	Statements	Never do it f (%age)	Seldom do it f (%age)	Mostly do it f (%age)	Always do it f (%age)
1	Except for contraindicated patients, elevate at an angle of 30–45 degrees the head of the bed.	6 (2.43%)	6 (2.43%)	112 (45.34%)	123 (49.80%)
2	Cuff pressure should be maintained at 20–30 cm H ₂ O.	8 (3.24%)	4 (1.62%)	222 (89.88%)	13 (5.26%)
3	Regularly check and control tracheal cuff pressure using a manual manometer.	10 (4.05%)	2 (0.81%)	114 (46.15%)	121 (48.99%)
4	Regularly check the proper positioning of the nasogastric tube.	55 (22.27%)	78 (31.58%)	101 (40.89%)	13 (5.26%)
5	Oral care is performed with chlorhexidine (0.12% or 2%).	5 (2.02%)	7 (2.83%)	47 (19.03%)	188 (76.11%)
6	Oral care is performed every 4–8 h.	7 (2.83%)	5 (2.02%)	221 (89.47%)	14 (5.67%)

8	Before deflating the cuff of an endotracheal tube, before moving the tube, or patient position change ensure that secretions are cleared from above the tube cuff.	10 (4.05%)	2 (0.81%)	125 (50.61%)	110 (44.53%)
9	Except for contraindicated patients, Daily Perform spontaneous awakening trials with sedatives turned off.	4 (1.62%)	8 (3.24%)	112 (45.34%)	123 (49.80%)
10	Daily perform spontaneous breathing trials once a day.	77 (31.17%)	34 (13.77%)	45 (18.22%)	91 (36.84%)
11	Change the ventilator circuit when it is visibly soiled or mechanically malfunctioning.	34 (13.77%)	65 (26.32%)	67 (27.13%)	81 (32.79%)
12	Do not flush condensate water from the ventilator circuit into the machine or onto the patient.	89 (36.03%)	34 (13.77%)	99 (40.08%)	27 (10.93%)
13	Use sterile water to fill ventilator humidifiers.	66 (26.72%)	88 (35.63%)	78 (31.58%)	15 (6.07%)
14	In patients using an open suction system, use a sterile disposable suction catheter and sterile water for each suction.	65 (26.32%)	34 (13.77%)	112 (45.34%)	36 (14.57%)
15	In patients using an closed suction system, a closed suction catheter should be used for each new patient.	44 (17.81%)	65 (26.32%)	102 (41.30%)	36 (14.57%)
16	Observe aseptic technique when managing the tracheostomy site and replacing the tracheostomy tube.	11 (4.45%)	1 (0.40%)	208 (84.21%)	27 (10.93%)
17	Do not use the oxygen tube, mask, and ambu bag used for one patient on another patient.	110 (44.53%)	112 (45.34%)	12 (4.86%)	13 (5.26%)

DISCUSSION

Based upon the analysis of the obtained data preventive bundles, together with the VAP checklist, play an important role in decreasing the incidence of this complication. According to the findings of this study, nurses must be more creative in their interventions. Current study results found that maintaining cuff pressure, oral care and following aseptic technique may prevent VAP. It was determined that oral care was an effective intervention to prevent hospital-acquired pneumonia by reducing pathogenic oral

microbial colonization.²⁸

In a study, it was found that chlorhexidine mouthwash or gel, as part of OHC, probably reduces the incidence of developing ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) in critically ill patients²⁹ consistent with current study findings. It was assumed that measures such as hand hygiene and aseptic suctioning technique were the most basic techniques and that they were taken for granted, along with all the other interventions for VAP prevention³⁰ is also in accordance with our study result findings.

Device-based cuff pressure monitoring was essential in maintaining adequate cuff pressure but often was inadequate, resulting in high readings. Therefore, device-based cuff pressure monitoring be practiced. Temporary drops in endotracheal cuff pressure were important for entry of upper airway secretions into the lower airways and increased in the incidence of VAP³¹ is comparative with this study result. However, chlorhexidine oral decontamination did not reduce the rate of ventilator-associated pneumonia in critically ill adult patients and its routine use could not be recommended³² is inconsistent with our study result.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, non-pharmacological approaches found to be effective in reducing VAP in critically ill patients included elevating head of the bed at an angle of 30–45 degrees, maintaining cuff pressure at 20–30 cm H₂O, oral care with chlorhexidine and following aseptic techniques before replacement of tracheostomy. Hence, total prevalence of VAP was 4.86% found in critically ill patients.

OUTCOMES & UTILIZATION

This study result addresses that VAP prevention measures must be carefully considered for resource needs and implementation barriers, such as limited staff and time constraints. A tailored VAP prevention bundle can address these challenges, incorporating team training, electronic reminders, checklists, and regular feedback. Using a VAP surveillance system, ensuring consistent hand hygiene, and elevating the patient's body position, which is a low-resource measure with proven efficacy, are useful strategies.

IMPLICATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Until more robust evidence emerges, the multidisciplinary team should carefully select VAP prevention measures. High-quality, randomized controlled trials, including cluster trials, are needed to establish the effectiveness of these interventions. Future studies should focus

on consistent VAP definitions, rigorous methodologies to minimize bias, and consideration of patient population diversity and clinical settings. These efforts will aim to improve patient safety, survival, and quality of life following critical care. Future studies should explore non-pharmacological interventions like early mobilization, targeted nutrition, appropriate nurse-patient ratios, and inter-professional communication, which show promise but require further investigation on their direct impact on VAP outcomes.

The study did provide answers to the questions whether and to what extent the shape of the artificial airway cuff contributed to the reduction of VAP. It also did not indicate which of the methods of VAP prevention (automatic constant pressure control in the cuff or automatic constant subglottic secretion suction) influenced the final effectiveness. All these elements should be considered together.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Although according to the design of the present study, the researchers were blinded to the fact thereby bringing about a bias. Since this is a single-center study, the results obtained may only be extrapolated to ICUs of similar characteristics with the same nurse/patient ratio and with similar workloads. Finally, the design of our study does not enable to determine any cause-and-effect relationship but rather the possible relationship between the variables of the study.

REFERENCES

- Udompat P, Rongmuang D, Hershov RC. Modifiable risk factors of ventilator-associated pneumonia in non-intensive care unit versus intensive care unit. *J Infect Dev Ctries.* 2021;15(10):1471–80. PMID: 34780370 DOI: 3855/jidc.14190
- Masyithah I, Hadi U, Koendhori EB. Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Dr. Soetomo General Hospital Surabaya. *JUXTA.* 2021;12(2):57-60. DOI: 20473/juxta. V12I22021.57-60

- Cooper, Adam S. Oral Hygiene Care to Prevent Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Critically Ill Patients. *Critical Care Nurse*. 2021;41(4):8082. doi:10.4037/ccn2021314.
- Rosenthal VD, Jin Z, Memish ZA, et al. Multinational prospective cohort study of rates and risk factors for ventilator-associated pneumonia over 24 years in 42 countries of Asia, Africa, Eastern Europe, Latin America, and the Middle East: findings of the International Nosocomial Infection Control Consortium (INICC). *Antimicrob Steward Healthc Epidemiol*. 2023; 3.
- Wu, D., Wu, C., Zhang, S. & Zhong, Y. Risk factors of ventilator-associated pneumonia in critically ill patients. *Front Pharm*. 2019; 10:482.
- Steen J, Vansteelandt S, de Bus L, Depuydt P, Gadeyne B, Benoit DD, et al. Attributable mortality of ventilator-associated pneumonia replicating findings, revisiting methods. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*. 2021;18(5):830-7. PMID: 33285078 DOI: 1513/AnnalsATS.202004-385OC
- Wicky PH, Niedermann MS, Timsit JF. Ventilator-associated pneumonia in the era of COVID-19 pandemic: How common and what is the impact? *Crit Care*. 2021;25(1):153.
- Sousa AS, Ferrito C, Paiva JA. Application of a ventilator associated pneumonia prevention guidelines and outcomes: A quasi-experimental study. *Intensive Crit Care Nurs*. 2019; 51:50-56.
- Abad CL, Formalejo CP, Mantaring DML. Assessment of knowledge and implementation practices of the ventilator acquired pneumonia (VAP) bundle in the intensive care unit of a private hospital. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control*. 2021;10(1):161.
- Pozuelo-Carrascosa DP et al. Body position for preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia for critically ill patients: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *J Intensive Care*. 2022; 10(1):9.
- Pozuelo-Carrascosa DP et al. Subglottic secretion drainage for preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia: an overview of systematic reviews and an updated meta-analysis. *Eur Respir Rev*. 2020; 29(155):190107.
- Sanaie S et al. Comparison of closed vs open suction in prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Indian J Crit Care Med*. 2022; 26(7):839-845.
- Silva PUJ, Paranhos LR, Meneses-Santos D, Blumenberg C, Macedo DR, Cardoso SV. Combination of toothbrushing and chlorhexidine compared with exclusive use of chlorhexidine to reduce the risk of ventilator-associated pneumonia: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Clinics [Internet]*. 2021;76:e2659.
- Dat VQ, Minh Yen L, Thi Loan H, et al. Effectiveness of continuous endotracheal cuff pressure control for the prevention of ventilator-associated respiratory infections: an open-label randomized, controlled trial. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2022; 74: 1795-1803.
- Divatia J.V., Pulinilkunnathil J.G., & Myatra S.N. Nosocomial Infections and Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Cancer Patients: In: Nates J., Price K. (eds). *Oncologic Critical Care*. 2020; 1419-1439.
- Huter K, Krick T, Domhoff D, Seibert K, Wolf-Ostermann K, Rothgang H. <p>Effectiveness of Digital Technologies to Support Nursing Care: Results of a Scoping Review</p> *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare [Internet]*. 2020; 13:1905-26.
- Fromentin M, Ricard JD, Roux D. Respiratory microbiome in mechanically ventilated patients: a narrative review. *Intensive Care Medicine [Internet]*. 2021;47(3):292-306.

- Kózka M, Sega A, Wojnar-Gruszka K, Tarnawska A, Gniadek A. Risk Factors of Pneumonia Associated with Mechanical Ventilation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* [Internet] 2020;17(2):656.
- National Healthcare Safety Network. Ventilator-associated (VAP) and Non-ventilator-associated Pneumonia (PNEU) Event. 2021.
- Howroyd F et al. Ventilator-associated pneumonia: pathobiological heterogeneity and diagnostic challenges. *Nat Commun*. 2024; 15(1):6447.
- Dewi YS, Qona'ah A, Arifin H, Pradipta RO, Rosita R, Benjamin LS. Bridging Innovation to Prevent Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia: A Descriptive Qualitative Study among Critical Care Nurses. *Jurnal Keperawatan Padjadjaran* [Internet]. 2021; 9:232-9.
- Mahmoodpoor A, Hamishehkar H, Asghari R, Abri R, Shadvar K, Sanaie S. Effect of a Probiotic Preparation on Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Critically Ill Patients Admitted to the Intensive Care Unit: A Prospective Double-Blind Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutr Clin Pract*. 2019;34(1):156-162. doi: 10.1002/ncp.10191
- Daniela Fradinho Almeida, Maria do Rosário Pinto, Maria Candida Duraó, Helga Rafael Henriques, Joana Ferreira Teixeira. Specialized nursing intervention on critically ill patients in the prevention of intubation-associated pneumonia: an integrative literature review. *Acute and Critical Care*. 2024;39(3):341-349
- Adam S. Cooper. Oral Hygiene Care to Prevent Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Critically Ill Patients. *Crit Care Nurse*. 2021;41(4):80-82.
- A. Halili, S. Ghafari, M. Saghaei et al. Prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia by a nose care program combining with oral care among patients hospitalized in intensive care units: a single-blind randomized controlled trial. *Medicina Clínica Práctica*. 2024; 7:100401
- Hudakova, T. Prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia in intensive departments from the nursing perspective. *Україна. Здоров'я нації*, 2020;2(3).
- Choi, M.-I., Han, S.-Y., Jeon, H.-S., Choi, E.-S., Won, S.-E., Lee, Y.-J., Yang, J.-H., Baek, C.-Y., Shim, H., & Mun, S.-J. The influence of professional oral hygiene care on reducing ventilator-associated pneumonia in trauma intensive care unit patients. *British Dental Journal*. 2022;232(4): 253-259.
- Rathbun KP, Bourgault AM, Sole ML. Oral Microbes in Hospital-Acquired Pneumonia: Practice and Research Implications. *Crit Care Nurse*. 2022
- Zhao T, Wu X, Zhang Q, Li C, Worthington HV, Hua F. Oral hygiene care for critically ill patients to prevent ventilator-associated pneumonia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2020
- Mastrogianni, M., Katsoulas, T., Galanis, P., Korompeli, A., & Myrianthefs, P. The Impact of Care Bundles on Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP) Prevention in Adult ICUs: A Systematic Review. *Antibiotics*.
- Biju Viswambharan, Manjini Jeyaram Kumari, Gopala Krishnan, Lakshmi Ramamoorthy. Under or overpressure: an audit of endotracheal cuff pressure monitoring at the tertiary care center *Acute and Critical Care*. 2021
- De Cassai, A., Pettenuzzo, T., Busetto, V. et al. Chlorhexidine is not effective at any concentration in preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *J Anesth Analg Crit*